

Fertility Breakthrough: Mesenchymal Stem Cells and Enhanced Endometrial

Receptivity - A Comprehensive Review

The Chinese University of Hong Kong

**Revolutionizing Reproductive Medicine: A Comprehensive
Literature Review on Mesenchymal Stem Cells and Their
Potential in Enhancing Endometrial Receptivity for Improved
Fertility Outcomes**

RMCE6003 Literature Review

Dissertation

**Submitted as a partial fulfillment for the
Degree of Master of Science in
Reproductive Medicine and Clinical Embryology**

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" அணுவில் அணுவினை ஆதிப் பிரானை அணுவில் அணுவினை
ஆயிரம் கூறிட்டு அணுவில் அணுவை அணுக வல்லார்கட்கு
அணுவில் அணுவை அணுகவும் ஆமே"திருமந்திரம்

Translation

*" The Supreme Being, who is the origin of all, exists within the smallest atom. For
Those who can perceive the atom within the atom, the divine essence becomes
accessible." ...Thirumannthiram*

Dedication

This work is dedicated to

My Parents, Family, and the Teachers of
Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology,
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Glossary

Abs: Apoptotic bodies (Abs)
AMCs: Amniotic Membrane-derived Mesenchymal Cells
ART: Assisted Reproductive Technologies
AS: Asherman's Syndrome
ASCs: adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cells
BMSCs: Bone marrow mesenchymal stromal cells
C-BMSC-exos: Cardiotrophin-1-modified bone marrow stem cell exosomes
CD: Cluster of Differentiation
CDYL: Chromodomain Y-like protein
CS: Collagen Scaffold
CXCR: Chemokine Receptor
E2: Estrogen
EA: Electro Acupuncture
ECM: Extra Cellular Matrix
EECs: Epithelial Endometrial Cells
EGF: Epidermal Growth Factor
ELISA: Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA)
EndMSCs: Endometrial-derived Mesenchymal Stem Cells
enMSCs: Endometrial mesenchymal stem cells
EnMSCs: Endometrial Mesenchymal Stem Cells
EnSCs: Endometrial Stromal Cells
EPCs: Endothelial Progenitor Cells
ER/PR: Estrogen receptor/progesterone receptor
ERA: Endometrial Receptivity Array (ERA)
ERt: Endometrial Receptivity test
FDAAM: Freeze Dried Acellular Amniotic Membrane
FET: Frozen Embryo Transfers
FSH: Follicular Stimulation Hormone
HA: Hyaluronic acid or hyaluronan (HA)
HAMSCs: Human Amniotic Mesenchymal Stem Cells
HLA-DR: Human Leukocyte Antigen – DR isotype
Hox genes: homeobox genes
hUCMSCs: human umbilical cord mesenchymal stem cells
ICSI: Intracytoplasmic sperm injection
IL: Interleukin
iPSCs: induced Pluripotent Stem Cells
ITGβ1: Integrin β 1
IUA: Intra Uterine Adhesion

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IVF: In Vitro Fertilization
LH: Luteinizing Hormone
LIFR: Leukemia Inhibitory Factor Receptor
menSCs: menstrual blood-derived Stromal Cells
miRNAs: microRNAs
MSCs: Mesenchymal Stem Cells
MVs: Micro Vesicles
NGS: Next Generation Sequencing
OPN: Osteopontin
P: Progesterone
PCOS: Poly Cystic Ovarian Syndrome
PDT: Population Doubling Time
PKH26: a fluorescent cell label
POF: Premature Ovarian Failure
PPCNg: Poly -polyethylene glycol citrate-co-N-isopropylacrylamide gelatin
PRP: Platelet Rich Plasma
RAS: Rat sarcoma virus: Ras
RIF: Recurrent Implantation Failure
RNA: Ribo Nucleic Acid
SDF-1: Stromal-Cell Derived factor-1
TGF: Tumor Growth Factor
Th: T helper
UCMSC-AAM: Umbilical Cord Mesenchymal Stem Cells incorporated into an amniotic membrane
UCSCs: Umbilical Cord Stem Cells
VEGF: Vasso Endothelial Growth Factor
WES: Whole Exome Sequencing
WGS: Whole Genome Sequencing
WJ-MSCs: Wharton's jelly Mesenchymal Stem Cells

1. Abstract

1.1 Background

Female infertility is a complex challenge influenced by genetic, lifestyle, and medical factors. While Assisted Reproductive Technologies (ART) offer promise, concerns persist, especially in Intracytoplasmic Sperm Injection (ICSI) cycles, with heightened perinatal risks and birth defects (Christodoulou et al., 2018). This review focuses on the evolution and application of mesenchymal stem cell (MSC) therapy as a potential solution, with an emphasis on endometrial receptivity as a key factor in reproductive success.

1.2 Objective and Rationale

The primary research question guiding this investigation is, "What is the existing understanding of the role of mesenchymal stem cells in enhancing endometrial receptivity and improving fertility outcomes?" This inquiry aims to fill the existing gaps in the literature, highlighting the paramount significance of endometrial receptivity during the window of implantation.

1.3 Search Methods

A systematic literature search was conducted across PubMed, Embase, and Web of Science, spanning the last decade. Fifty-nine relevant articles were selected based

on predefined criteria, including study design, participant characteristics, MSC type, administration route, and key outcomes related to endometrial receptivity and fertility. Rigorous assessment of article quality and analysis of bias were integral components of the inclusion/exclusion criteria.

1.4 Outcomes

The review outlines MSCs' potential to promote endometrial receptivity through regenerative, immunomodulatory, and trophic effects. Molecular evidence supports their role in regulating gene expression and signaling pathways crucial for implantation. Ethical considerations and challenges associated with MSC therapy are discussed, underscoring the need for ongoing research and vigilant monitoring to ensure safety and efficacy.

1.5 Wider Implications

This review offers a comprehensive viewpoint on the utilization of MSCs to enhance endometrial receptivity, providing valuable insights for future research and clinical advancements in the field of reproductive medicine. The discussion encompasses the impact on basic science research, potential implications for clinical practice, and the significance for reproductive clinicians and scientists. The ethical considerations highlighted underscore the importance of responsible advancements in this field.

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Keywords: *Female infertility, Assisted Reproductive Technologies (ART), Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), Endometrial receptivity, Intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI), Reproductive success. Implantation window, Molecular evidence, Ethical considerations, Fertility outcomes.*

2 Introduction

In the face of the worldwide landscape of reproductive health challenges, infertility emerges as a complex and multifaceted dilemma, influenced by a diverse range of factors, spanning from genetic predispositions to the repercussions of unfavorable lifestyle choices (Wu et al., 2022). Female infertility is caused by various factors, like surgeries in the pelvic or inguinal areas, issues with egg development, problems with ovulation, dysfunction of the ovaries, and damage or blockage in the fallopian tubes. (Abuwala & Tal, 2021).

Figure 1: Human Mesenchymal Stem Cells (Cen et al., 2022)

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Type of Stem Cell	Origin	Function	Usage
Embryonic Stem Cells	Derived from early-stage embryos	Differentiate into any cell type in the body	Research, Regenerative Medicine
Adult Stem Cells (Mesenchymal)	Various tissues (bone marrow, adipose tissue, etc.)	Maintain and repair tissues by differentiating into specific cell types	Regenerative Medicine, Tissue Engineering
Hematopoietic Stem Cells	Bone marrow, blood	Generate all types of blood cells (red blood cells, white blood cells, platelets)	Bone Marrow Transplants, Blood Disorders Treatment
Neural Stem Cells	Nervous system (brain, spinal cord)	Generate neurons and supporting cells in the nervous system	Neurological Disorders Treatment, Research
Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells	Generated from adult cells by reprogramming	Similar to embryonic stem cells, can differentiate into any cell type	Disease Modeling, Drug Discovery, Regenerative Medicine
Menstrual Stem Cells	Menstrual Blood	Differentiate into various cell types, including adipocytes, osteocytes, chondrocytes, and neurons	Regenerative Medicine, Tissue Engineering, Disease Treatment
Dental Pulp Stem Cells	Dental Pulp	Differentiate into various cell types, including odontoblasts, neural-like cells, and osteoblasts	Dental Tissue Engineering, Regenerative Dentistry
Amniotic Fluid Stem Cells	Amniotic Fluid	Differentiate into various cell types, including muscle, bone, fat, and nerve cells	Regenerative Medicine, Tissue Engineering
Umbilical Cord Blood Stem Cells	Umbilical Cord Blood	Generate blood cells and support hematopoiesis	Hematopoietic Stem Cell Transplantation, Blood Disorders
Adipose-Derived Stem Cells	Adipose Tissue	Differentiate into various cell types, including adipocytes, osteoblasts, and chondrocytes	Regenerative Medicine, Cosmetic Surgery
Endometrial Stem Cells	Uterine Endometrium	Differentiate into various cell types, including epithelial and stromal cells	Endometrial Regeneration, Reproductive Medicine
Olfactory Stem Cells	Olfactory Epithelium	Generate neurons involved in the sense of smell	Olfactory Dysfunction Treatment, Research
Epithelial Stem Cells	Skin, Gastrointestinal tract, etc.	Regenerate and maintain epithelial tissues	Wound Healing, Tissue Repair
Cardiac Stem Cells	Heart Tissue	Differentiate into heart muscle cells	Cardiac Regeneration, Heart Disease Treatment
Endothelial Stem Cells	Blood Vessels	Contribute to the formation of new blood vessels (angiogenesis)	Vascular Regeneration, Ischemic Disease Treatment
Hair Follicle Stem Cells	Hair Follicles	Regenerate hair follicles and surrounding tissues	Hair Regeneration, Skin Wound Healing
Intestinal Stem Cells	Intestinal Epithelium	Regenerate intestinal epithelium and maintain gut homeostasis	Intestinal Repair, Inflammatory Bowel Disease Treatment
Skeletal Muscle Stem Cells	Skeletal Muscle Tissue	Repair and regenerate skeletal muscle fibers	Muscle Regeneration, Muscle Disorders Treatment

Table 1: Types of Stem cells

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The global prevalence of female infertility is estimated to range from 8 to 12% (Guo et al., 2023). While Assisted Reproductive Technologies (ART) hold promise in amplifying pregnancy rates, they grapple with challenges germane to gametic regeneration and modulation of the immune system (Zhao et al., 2015).

Widespread reports highlight the risks associated with the use of assisted reproductive technology (ART) in the treatment of infertility, revealing elevated perinatal risks and a greater occurrence of birth (Zakrzewski W et al., 2019).

Following ICSI cycles, there's a concerning doubling of major birth defect risks impacting cardiovascular, genitourinary, and musculoskeletal systems. Notably, ICSI comprises 70% of global treatment cycles, heightening the need to address these concerns urgently (Jin-Xiang Wu et al., 2022).

Despite advancements in reproductive medicine, challenges remain for optimal fertility outcomes globally. Innovative solutions arise through stem cell techniques, renowned for their extensive proliferative capacity (Wu et al., 2022), replicative potential, and capacity to differentiate into diverse tissue-specific cells, are classified into adult stem cells, early embryonic stem cells, and induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) based on their origins.

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While adult stem cells, particularly MSCs (Hosoya et al., 2022), have demonstrated widespread utility in clinical treatments, their application is ensnared in ethical and safety controversies.

A significant breakthrough emerges with umbilical cord stem cells (UCSTCs), showing success in Phase I clinical trials for treating infertility due to intrauterine adhesions (IUA). These trials reveal no serious adverse events, with some participants achieving healthy offspring births.

A promising avenue in this pursuit unfolds within the realm of regenerative medicine, specifically through the utilization of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) (Tabeeva et al., 2023).

Subfertility complexities fuel interest in non-traditional ART, especially MSCs. These complexities compound challenges for couples seeking conception, sparking growing interest in non-traditional ART, notably MSCs.

Adult stem cells like MSCs could transform reproductive medicine. They aid tissue repair and modulate immunity, promising solutions for subfertility. Recent studies highlight their role in releasing growth factors and cytokines, potentially enhancing ovarian function and endometrial receptivity for embryo development.

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Regenerative medicine intersects with reproductive health, promising innovative solutions for fertility enhancement. Our review scrutinizes the advancements in MSC therapy for infertility treatment, emphasizing its efficacy and novel approach. We specifically focus on its role in improving endometrial receptivity, providing a nuanced analysis of the subject.

Objective and Rationale

This review examines MSCs) potential in enhancing fertility outcomes by improving endometrial receptivity. Through systematic analysis of existing research, it assesses MSCs' mechanisms and their impact on subfertility factors such as oocyte quality, sperm function, and endometrial receptivity. Evaluation of research and preclinical studies establishes a scientific rationale for further exploring MSC-based therapies in subfertility treatment.

2.1 Research Question

" What is the existing understanding of the role of mesenchymal stem cells in enhancing endometrial receptivity and improving fertility outcomes?"

2.2 Significance of the Study

Understanding the interplay between MSCs and endometrial receptivity is crucial for advancing reproductive medicine.

This review addresses a critical gap in the literature by providing a comprehensive synthesis of current knowledge, highlighting the potential of MSCs as a therapeutic tool. Insights gained from this review may inform future research directions, clinical applications, and contribute to the development of innovative strategies for managing infertility.

3 Methodology:

3.1 Method

	Aspect	Details
1	Search Strategy	Electronic databases used: PubMed, Embase, Web of Science Search terms: "mesenchymal stem cells," "endometrial receptivity," "fertility outcomes" Inclusion criteria: Studies published in the last 12 years, peer-reviewed articles, clinical trials, and experimental studies on MSCs and endometrial receptivity
2	Study Selection	Initial articles found: 842 After removing duplicates: 786 Final selection after two-stage screening: 59
3	Data Extraction	Extracted information: Study design, participant characteristics, MSC type, administration route, key outcomes related to endometrial receptivity and fertility
4	Quality Assessment	Tools used: Cochrane risk of bias tool for clinical trials Considerations: Study design, sample size, methodology, and other relevant factors
5	Data Synthesis	Organization: Studies grouped based on key outcomes or interventions Analysis: Descriptive statistics or qualitative synthesis as appropriate
6	Critical Appraisal	Assessment of limitations and strengths of included studies Implications: Discussion of findings for future research and clinical practice

Table 2: Methods of Review

3.2 Search Strategy

A recent review looked at studies from the past decade on how MSCs influence endometrial receptivity and fertility outcomes. They searched PubMed, Embase, and Web of Science, covering both experimental and clinical research.

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Flow Chart: Identification of Studies

3.3 Study Selection

Initially, 842 articles were retrieved. After removing duplicates, a two-stage screening process based on title and abstract was conducted. Studies meeting predefined inclusion criteria underwent full-text review. Finally, 59 articles were selected based on relevance, quality, and research design.

3.4 Inclusion criteria

Studies published in the last 12 years, peer-reviewed articles with open resources with no objection to use its contents with citation, to another review clinical trials, and experimental studies related to mesenchymal stem cells and endometrial receptivity.

3.5 Exclusion criteria

Studies with irrelevant outcomes, animal studies that do not have implications for human fertility, and studies with a low level of evidence with the copy right articles.

3.6 Data Extraction

Selected studies provided data on study design, participant characteristics, MSC type, administration route, and key outcomes related to endometrial receptivity and fertility. Methodological quality was assessed using appropriate tools for experimental and clinical research.

3.7 Quality Assessment

Using established tools for quality assessment and Considered study design, sample size, methodology, and other relevant factors

3.8 Data Synthesis

Organized the studies based on key outcomes or interventions.

3.9 Critical Appraisal

Critically appraise the limitations and strengths of the included studies. Discussed the implications of the findings for future research and clinical practice.

4 Data Collection, Data Organization and Data Analysis

4.1 Endometrial Receptivity

Endometrial receptivity refers to the ability of the endometrium, the lining of the uterus, to receive and support the implantation of a fertilized egg (embryo). The endometrium goes through a series of changes during the menstrual cycle in response to hormonal fluctuations. These changes are essential for creating an optimal environment for embryo implantation (Bajpai et al., 2023).

Endometrial receptivity, key for embryo attachment during the implantation window (days 19 to 21 of a 28-day cycle) in IVF, is evaluated using ultrasound and biomarkers.

Improving receptivity boosts implantation and pregnancy success. A uterine lining thickness below 7 mm signals suboptimal conditions for embryo transfer (Tersoglio et al., 2020).

Causes of a thin endometrium may include inflammation like acute or chronic endometritis, iatrogenic factors such as repeated curettage or polypectomy, hysteroscopic interventions like myomectomy, laparoscopic procedures opening the uterine cavity, and misuse of clomiphene citrate. Unique uterine structural patterns could also contribute (Tersoglio et al., 2020).

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Endometrial receptivity is pivotal for fertility, influencing a woman's ability to conceive and maintain a pregnancy. During the implantation window in the menstrual cycle, the endometrial lining must be ideally receptive for successful embryo attachment. Disruptions in this process can hinder pregnancy. (Zhao et al., 2021).

Following table explaining the morphological features of endometrium during the menstrual cycle and corresponding molecular markers to assess them.

Menstrual Cycle Phase	Days	Hormonal Changes	Morphological Features	Molecular Markers
Menstrual (Days 1-5)	1-5	Low estrogen and progesterone	Shedding of the endometrial lining	-
Proliferative (Days 6-14)	6-14	Rising estrogen levels	Thickening of the endometrial lining, increased blood flow	Increased expression of estrogen receptors
Ovulatory (Day 15)	15	Surge in luteinizing hormone (LH)	Ovulation occurs	Increased expression of LH receptors
Early Luteal (Days 16-18)	16-18	Increased progesterone	Glandular and stromal changes, vascularization	Increased expression of progesterone receptors
Mid-Luteal (Days 19-23)	19-23	Sustained high progesterone	Increased glandular secretion, spiral artery development	Increased expression of integrins, pinopodes
Late Luteal (Days 24-28)	24-28	Declining progesterone if no pregnancy	Pre-menstrual changes, breakdown of the endometrial tissue	Decreased expression of integrins, pinopodes

Table 3: Endometrial Changes (Darz et al., 2016)

In subfertility, Recurrent Implantation Failure (RIF) is a notable challenge marked by repeated unsuccessful embryo implantation attempts. This failure often stems from issues with endometrial receptivity, underscoring the crucial interplay between the embryo and the uterine environment for successful implantation (Zhankina et al., 2021).

Factors like thin endometrium, luteal phase defects, hormonal imbalances, uterine abnormalities, chronic endometritis, age-related changes, and certain medications can hinder endometrial receptivity. (Barkholt et al., 2013).

Subtle disruptions in endometrial receptivity may contribute to unexplained infertility, despite no identified cause. Addressing these factors is crucial in fertility treatments, improving chances of successful conception. (Wang et al., 2016).

4.2 Endometrial Receptivity Assessment

Endometrial receptivity testing pinpoints the optimal time for embryo transfer into the uterus, known as the implantation window. It entails extracting a biopsy from the endometrial lining and scrutinizing gene expression within the tissue.

By utilizing a computational predictor, these results aim to pinpoint the optimal period for embryo implantation. The endometrial state is typically categorized as receptive, pre-receptive, or post-receptive (Zhang et al., 2022).

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Treatment cycles include a "personalized embryo transfer" aligned with the identified optimal implantation window. This aims to boost successful implantation and pregnancy chances (Fan et al., 2023).

Concerns persist about the test's accuracy in predicting the optimal implantation window and its consistency across treatment cycles. Inaccurate results or varying windows between cycles could diminish the procedure's contribution to successful pregnancy.

The Endometrial Receptivity Array (ERA) is a specific type of endometrial receptivity test. However, current evidence does not support its daily use. Further research is required to ascertain its effectiveness before considering wider application (Garcia-Velasco et al., 2023).

RIF occurs despite addressing endometrial factors with antibiotics and Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP). We applied Mesenchymal Stem Cells (MSCs) mixed with PRP in 29 cases, improving outcomes in 23.

Implicated factors include Platelet and Endothelial Cell Adhesion Molecule 1, Transforming Growth Factor Beta, and Chromodomain Y-like protein (CDYL) (Kochar Kaur et al., 2020).

4.3 Mesenchymal Stem Cells (MSCs)

MSCs are a type of multipotent stromal cells that can differentiate into a variety of cell types (Mansouri-Kivaj et al., 2023). They are found in various tissues throughout the body, including bone marrow, adipose tissue (fat), umbilical cord, and other connective tissues.

MSCs can self-renew and differentiate into mesodermal cells like osteoblasts, adipocytes, and chondrocytes. Hafner demonstrates their effectiveness in treating tissue injuries, as seen in a successful spinal cord injury case where injecting autologous adipose tissue-derived MSCs notably restored motor and sensory functions (Hafner, 2019).

MSCs have key roles in regenerative medicine, possessing multipotency to differentiate into various cell types vital for tissue repair. Their immunomodulatory properties make them promising for immune-related disorder treatments, exerting anti-inflammatory effects and regulating immune cell activity.

Another key attribute of MSCs is their trophic effects. These cells can secrete a range of growth factors and cytokines that play a crucial role in promoting tissue repair and regeneration. This trophic support enhances the regenerative potential of surrounding cells and facilitates the healing process.

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The low immunogenicity of MSCs is noteworthy, potentially allowing for allogeneic transplantation with reduced risk of immune rejection. This characteristic enhances the feasibility of using MSCs for therapy.

Additionally, MSCs can be isolated from diverse sources such as bone marrow, adipose tissue, and umbilical cord, offering flexibility for tailored therapeutic applications. Overall, these features underscore the promise of MSCs for innovative approaches in regenerative medicine and treating various medical conditions.

4.4 Harvesting Mesenchymal Stem Cells (MSCs)

MSCs present a versatile therapeutic potential, with collection from various tissues pivotal for their application in regenerative medicine. Among the most established sources is bone marrow, recognized for its relatively high MSC concentration, obtained via minimally invasive bone marrow aspiration.

Figure 2: Harvesting of Mesenchymal Stem cells (Costela-Ruiz et al., 2022)

Adipose tissue, abundant in areas like the abdomen and thighs, is another common source collected through liposuction, providing readily accessible and widely used MSCs (Sudoma et al., 2019).

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Figure 3: Harvesting MSC from Endometrium and Menstrual Blood (Darz et al., 2016)

Figure 3 illustrate the procedures involving the harvesting of MSCs from the endometrium and the menstrual blood (Darz et al., 2016)

Umbilical cord tissue, especially Wharton's jelly, and placenta-derived MSCs are valuable sources for research and clinical use. Peripheral blood, although with lower MSC concentrations, can be obtained via apheresis.

Other origins include dental pulp, synovial fluid, and amniotic fluid. Source selection factors include access, therapeutic goals, and patient-specific needs, showcasing MSCs' versatility in regenerative medicine (Mansouri-Kivaj et al., 2023).

4.5 MSCs and Reproductive Health

MSCs are promising for enhancing endometrial receptivity in regenerative medicine and reproductive health. Their regenerative abilities facilitate tissue repair and regeneration in the endometrium by differentiating into various cell types, including endometrial cells.

Additionally, MSCs exert anti-inflammatory effects (Policastro et al., 2015), mitigating chronic inflammation in the endometrial environment that could otherwise adversely impact receptivity. Following figure 4 explain the uses of MSC in Asherman`s syndrome.

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Figure 4: MSC in Ashermans` s Syndrome(Strug & Aghajanova, 2021)

MSCs foster immune tolerance in the endometrium, preventing embryo rejection, and stimulate angiogenesis for adequate blood supply during implantation. Their paracrine signaling supports endometrial growth, while ECM remodeling facilitates embryo attachment.

MSCs interact with hormonal signaling pathways, potentially stimulating endometrial secretion, showcasing a multifaceted approach to optimizing receptivity. This highlights their potential as a valuable therapeutic tool in reproductive medicine. Ongoing research delves into these mechanisms, aiming to improve fertility outcomes.

4.6 Molecular Evidence of MSCs and Improving Endometrial Receptivity

The endometrium, comprising basal and functional layers, is crucial for embryo implantation and menstruation. Successful pregnancy relies on a coordinated interaction between a high-quality embryo and the endometrium. Recurrent implantation failure (RIF) arises when good-quality embryos fail to implant despite multiple transfers.

The underlying causes may arise from issues related to the embryo, the mother, or a combination of both. Recent studies have closely linked RIF to irregularities in endometrial function (Jin-Xiang Wu et al., 2022).

Figure 5: Regrowing of Endometrium (Tabeeva et al., 2023)

Tabeeva et al. discuss the applications of MSCs in angiogenesis and mesenchymal-epithelial transition in the diagram above. The investigation into endometrial receptivity is evolving through sophisticated molecular techniques. MicroRNAs (miRNAs), small but influential RNA molecules, are being examined for their post-transcriptional gene regulatory roles, particularly in implantation and embryo receptivity.

Figure 6: Monitoring HUMSC and exosome hydrogel in rat endometrium via fluorescence (Zhang et al., 2022)

In vivo tracing of HUMSC and HUMSC-exosome hydrogel involved capturing IVIS images (Figure 6) depicting their retention in a rat model with a thin

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endometrium at different time points post intrauterine injection, both in vivo and in vitro (C). Quantification of fluorescence intensity in the HUMSC and HUMSC-exosome groups was conducted following intrauterine injection in a live rat model with a thin endometrium (Zhang et al., 2022).

Proteomic profiling unveils dynamic protein landscapes in the endometrium across menstrual phases, shedding light on receptivity signaling pathways. Biomarker discovery involves proteins, genes, and miRNAs.

Transcriptomics reveals crucial genes and pathways. Epigenetic modifications regulate gene expression. Immune microenvironment investigations explore cell populations and cytokines for embryo tolerance. Extracellular vesicles, like exosomes, carry molecular signals.

Single-cell analysis identifies key receptivity cell types. In vitro models with human endometrial cells enable controlled studies. Genomic and epigenomic analyses offer personalized insights into receptivity-related modifications, guiding precise fertility interventions.

Temporal and spatial variations in endometrial function result from hormonal regulation and paracrine factors, potentially causing dysfunction. Uterine factors impacting pregnancy include adhesions, thin endometrium, and inadequate growth. Asherman's syndrome (AS), often post-uterine surgeries, results from intrauterine

adhesions due to basal layer injury or endometriosis, reducing viable endometrial surface and impairing fertility, leading to recurrent miscarriage.

Figure 7: Trans differentiation of MSCs in to endometrium (Cen et al., 2022)

As described Figure 7, Cen et al. suggest stem cells for endometrial regeneration in intrauterine adhesions.

They transplanted menSCs from seven AS patients, restoring endometrial morphology and thickness. Notably, three refractory AS patients achieved post-menSC transplantation pregnancies (Cen et al., 2022).

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A team of Australian researchers has discovered and characterized a population of MSCs and epithelial progenitor cells in the human endometrium (Sudoma et al., 2019).

Low endometrial receptivity, common among reproductive-aged women, significantly hampers embryo implantation, especially in those with a thin endometrium.

Stem cell therapy, effective for various conditions, shows promise for thin endometrium, particularly with menstrual blood-derived mesenchymal stem cells regulating the EGF/Ras p21 pathway. (Zhao et al., 2021).

Although clear gold standards or definitive markers for identifying MSCs are lacking, the International Association of Cell Therapy established minimum criteria in 2006 (Christodoulou et al., 2018).

According to these criteria, MSCs must adhere to the culture surface under standard conditions, express specific markers (CD73, CD90, CD105), and not express certain other markers (CD11b, CD19, CD34, CD45, CD79a, HLA-DR). Additionally, MSCs must demonstrate the ability to differentiate into adipocytes, chondroblasts, and osteoblasts in vitro (Rojewski et al., 2008).

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The study examined menstrual stem cells (MenSCs) derived from both healthy women and those with a thin endometrium, assessing their influence on the invasiveness, proliferation, and angiogenesis of epithelial endometrial cells (EECs).

Results from the characterization process indicated that MenSCs sourced from women with a thin endometrium promoted the proliferation and invasion of EECs, with no observed impact on apoptosis (Zhao et al., 2021).

Upon conducting immunohistochemistry in an advanced age group, it was found that the expression levels of LIFR, ER, and PR in the endometrium were higher than those observed in younger patients.

However, no discernible differences were detected between the groups concerning other markers of endometrial receptivity, namely HOXA10 and OPN (Guo et al., 2023).

Another observation made and the progression of endometrial thickness on an individual basis is depicted in connection to the intervention with enMSCs, confirming a consistent increase of over 8 mm in all instances (Tersoglio et al., 2020).

In the following graph of Figure 8, Tersoglio et al demonstrates that improving the thickness of endometrium after intervention with MSCs.

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Figure 8: Improving Endometrial Thickness with MSCs (Tersoglio et al., 2020)

In vitro, MSC apoptotic bodies (ABs) boosted macrophage modulation, cell proliferation, and angiogenesis through increased mitochondrial bioenergetics. Combining ABs with HA hydrogel facilitated controlled release, promoting endometrial regeneration and treating intrauterine adhesions in murine and rat models, indicating clinical promise (Xin et al., 2022).

Another study indicates that BMSCs may be crucial in regenerating thin endometrium through homing, differentiating into diverse cell types, and exhibiting immunomodulation.

This highlights a promising cell therapy for thin endometrium, emphasizing the need for additional research into BMSCs' differentiation mechanisms (Zhao et al.,

2015). Gao et al states that Invasive uterine procedures can lead to issues like IUA and premature ovarian failure (POF). Mesenchymal stem cells show promise in treating these conditions, overcoming safety and cost concerns.

Extracellular vesicles from MSCs could be a promising tool for restoring reproductive function (Gao et al., 2022). Stem cells, specifically adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cells (ASCs), present an alternative for intrauterine adhesion (IUA) treatment. Combining ASC implantation with HA gel improves uterine conditions, reduces fibrosis, and enhances LIF expression, promising effective infertility treatment (Xu et al., 2021).

Figure 9: hUCMSCs aid severe endometrial damage recovery in rats. (Zhuang et al., 2022)

As mentioned in the Figure 9, an investigation demonstrated that the introduction of human umbilical cord mesenchymal stem cells (hUCMSCs) contributed to the

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healing of significant endometrial damage in rats. The study implies that the repair of the endometrium may involve mechanisms related to homing and paracrine signaling (Zhuang et al., 2022)

Sapozhak et al. highlight cultured endometrial MSCs expressing various bioactive elements, including growth factors, cytokines, and hormones such as interferon- γ -inducible protein 10, interleukin-1 receptor antagonist, vascular endothelial growth factor, interleukin-6, granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor, basic fibroblast growth factor, interleukin-8, interferon- γ , and monocyte chemoattractant protein 1. They propose that this combination could improve endometrial receptivity, even in cases of suboptimal tissue thickness, as seen clinically (Sapozhak et al., 2020).

In autoimmune premature ovarian failure (POF) mice, the study investigates the impact of human umbilical cord-derived mesenchymal stem cell (hUMSC) transplantation on ovarian function and endometrial receptivity. Post-transplantation, there was an increase in serum levels of E2, P, and IL-4, coupled with a decrease in FSH, IFN- γ , and IL-2 levels.

Healthy follicles saw a rise, while atresia follicles diminished. Notably, the HOXA10 gene expression increased, and CD56⁺CD16⁻ uterine natural killer cells decreased in the uterine endometrium. Furthermore, a significant reduction in the Th1/Th2 cytokine ratio was observed (Lu et al., 2019).

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BMSCs offer convenient harvesting, immune rejection avoidance, and multi-differentiation potential for tissue repair. Transplantation, particularly through intrauterine injection, proves effective in treating conditions like thin endometrium and intrauterine adhesions (Mansouri-Kivaj et al., 2023).

Molecular evidence supports their positive impact, with intrauterine injection demonstrating superior efficacy compared to vein injection. This study introduces a novel method for delivering BMSCs in the treatment of intrauterine adhesions (Wang et al., 2016).

A study showed that caprine endometrial mesenchymal stem cells (EnMSCs) resemble traditional MSCs morphologically and display confirmed differentiation potential. Population doubling time (PDT) analysis revealed that EnMSCs from anestrus goats could yield more cells in less time.

Given their normal karyotype and ability to differentiate into multiple cell lineages, En-MSCs present a promising avenue for stem cell therapies and serve as a readily available source for regenerative medicine studies in animal models (Tamadon et al., 2017).

The transplantation of umbilical cord mesenchymal stem cells incorporated into an amniotic membrane (UCMSC-AAM) has been shown to enhance the proliferation of both endometrial epithelial and stromal cells. The use of a fibrin-based tissue

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adhesive (FDAAM) has facilitated the evaluation of safety and standardized production processes, paving the way for potential clinical applications in the future (Wang et al., 2021).

Co-culturing Non-Thin Endometrium-MenSCs or TE-MenSCs with EECs differently enhanced endothelial progenitor cell activities. TE-MenSCs specifically promoted inflammation, vascularization, and matrix-related proteins via the EGF/Ras p21 pathway (Zhao et al., 2021).

Chen et al. claims that they have developed an injectable hydrogel with GelMA and SerMA, promoting angiogenesis and endometrial regeneration for fertility recovery using hUMSC (Chen et al., 2022).

A study explored using 10 million umbilical cord mesenchymal stem cells (UC-MSCs) on a collagen scaffold (CS) for Asherman syndrome. After two cycles, hysteroscopy assessed the uterine cavity, followed by frozen embryo transfers (FET) in the next cycle.

Findings suggest CS/UC-MSCs may enhance endometrial growth in unresponsive thin endometrium by promoting angiogenesis and improving endometrial hormone response (Zhang et al., 2021).

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Another study with Amniotic membrane-derived mesenchymal cells (AMCs) shows similarities with mare endometrial cells, expressing genes related to early pregnancy.

AMCs, especially with added progesterone, support endometrial cell proliferation, making them promising for treating endometrial issues in mares (Corradetti et al., 2014).

According to recent study, Endometrial-derived Mesenchymal Stem Cells (endMSCs) play a crucial role in regenerating the human endometrium through extracellular vesicles (EV-endMSCs). Comprehensive proteomic and transcriptomic analyses revealed enriched proteins linked to immune response, apoptosis regulation, and signaling pathways.

Inflammatory priming induced significant changes in the vesicle protein profile. MicroRNA analysis identified crucial regulators affecting cellular processes. This study unveils the intricate molecular networks in EV-endMSCs, highlighting their therapeutic potential as immunomodulatory agents for inflammatory conditions (Marinero et al., 2019).

Gurung et al. found that A83-01, a TGF- β receptor inhibitor, enhances perivascular, clonogenic mesenchymal stem/stromal cells (eMSCs) in vitro. Transcriptome

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analysis showed 1206 differentially expressed genes, indicating enriched anti-inflammatory, angiogenic, and proliferative processes.

TGF- β , Wnt, and Akt signaling pathways decreased, while anti-fibrotic and anti-apoptotic genes increased. A83-01-treated eMSCs exhibited heightened potency, highlighting potential applications in regenerative medicine. (Gurung et al., 2018).

Marino et al. emphasizes Wharton's jelly mesenchymal stem cells (WJ-MSCs) as a subset with significant differentiative potential, immunoprivileged status, and ethical ease of access. Resembling embryonic stem cells, WJ-MSCs exhibit shorter doubling time, superior expansion capacity, and immunomodulatory properties.

They effectively manage graft-versus-host disease, even in partially HLA-mismatched cases. The article also covers ongoing clinical trials and potential applications in regenerative medicine. (Marino et al., 2019).

Adding extracellular vesicles from endometrial-derived mesenchymal stem cells (EV-endMSCs) to embryo culture improved mouse oocyte development. Proteomic analysis identified fertilization-related proteins. In the mouse model, EV-endMSCs enhanced embryo quality, increased blastomere count, and influenced gene expression tied to oxidative stress and pluripotency.

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This suggests potential benefits for assisted reproduction in humans, improving implantation success and delivery rates for older oocytes. (Marinaro et al., 2019).

In RIF and non-RIF cases, endometrial mesenchymal stem cells show different receptivity marker expression. RIF associates with lower ITG β 1, higher HOXA11, and ITG β 3. Implications for receptivity and pregnancy establishment warrant further study (Esmaeilzadeh et al., 2020).

Similar study explores the potential of BMSCs in repairing heat-damaged rat endometrium. Transplanted BMSCs, identified by PKH26 labeling, localized to the damaged site, restoring endometrial structure, reducing fibrosis, and enhancing fertility.

Increased expression of integrin α v β 3 and leukemia inhibitory factor (LIF) suggests improved endometrial receptivity, highlighting BMSCs' reparative and beneficial effects (Wang et al., 2021).

Piltonen et al. discovered distinctive gene expression patterns in endometrial cells from PCOS women, indicating inflammation and pro-oncogenic changes. This is evident regardless of body mass index, particularly in ePPCOS and eMSCPCOS compared to controls (Piltonen et al., 2013).

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The findings suggest a distinct endometrial disease phenotype in PCOS women, potentially impacting endometrial function and long-term health (Piltonen et al., 2013).

Another study supports that This in vitro study aimed to characterize MSC from ectopic and eutopic endometrial tissue in patients with and without endometriosis.

Ectopic endometrial MSCs exhibited higher proliferation, migration, and angiogenic potential than eutopic or control MSCs (Lin et al., 2022). Treatment with the tyrosine kinase inhibitor Sorafenib treatment reduced ectopic MSC aberrations, including proliferation, motility, ezrin phosphorylation, vascular endothelial growth factor release, and hypoxia-inducible factor-1a expression. Targeting this MSC population, especially with sorafenib, may combat endometriotic implants (Moggio et al., 2012).

Study confirms endometriosis involves ectopic endometrial growth. Retrograde transport of EnSCs contributes to lesions. Epigenetic modulation in MSCs offers potential for treatment (Szukiewicz et al., 2021).

Sapozhak et al talks on addressing thin endometrium syndrome causing fertility challenges, a 38-year-old woman underwent unsuccessful assisted reproductive cycles.

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This case highlights the use of mesenchymal stem cells from the human endometrium to enhance endometrial receptivity. The protocol involved obtaining and utilizing these cells, resulting in improved endometrial functionality and increased chances of pregnancy through assisted reproductive technologies (Sapozhak et al., 2020).

Perrini et al. study the paracrine interaction of amniotic mesenchymal stem cell (AMC)-derived microvesicles (MVs) with endometrial cells. They explore MVs' effect on lipopolysaccharide-induced stress, revealing AMC-secreted MVs in the 100-200 nm size range (Perrini et al., 2016).

Over 72 hours, MVs reduced apoptosis, enhanced cell proliferation, suppressed pro-inflammatory gene expression, and mitigated the release of inflammatory cytokines, suggesting a potential role in alleviating endometrial inflammation in vivo (Perrini et al., 2016).

another study investigates the combined therapeutic effects of BMSC transplantation and electroacupuncture (EA) in a rat model of thin endometrium.

EA enhances BMSC migration to damaged uteri through the SDF-1/CXCR4 axis, leading to improved endometrial morphology, increased expression of cytoskeletal markers, elevated secretion of growth factors, and enhanced embryo implantation

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rates. EA supports BMSC-mediated repair of thin endometrium by promoting migration and enhancing paracrine effects (Xia et al., 2019).

In addressing unresponsive thin endometrium in Asherman syndrome (AS), a novel approach involved two consecutive transplants of umbilical cord mesenchymal stem cells loaded onto a collagen scaffold in 18 infertile women. Post-treatment, endometrial thickness significantly increased, improving pregnancy outcomes.

Immunohistochemical analysis showed enhanced endometrial angiogenesis, proliferation, and hormone responsiveness. This promising therapeutic strategy demonstrated safety and efficacy for refractory thin endometrium in AS (Zhang et al., 2021).

Study of Huang et al explores the therapeutic potential of human amniotic mesenchymal stem cells (hAMSCs) combined with a thermoresponsive biomaterial (PPCNg) for intrauterine adhesion (IUA) treatment. In vitro, hAMSCs cultured with PPCNg exhibited normal characteristics and multilineage differentiation potential.

In a rat IUA model, PPCNg/hAMSCs transplantation enhanced endometrial regeneration, evidenced by increased thickness, gland number, and reduced fibrosis. Immunohistochemistry revealed improved biomarker expression, and

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higher embryo implantation and pregnancy rates confirmed the effectiveness of this combined therapy for IUA (Huang et al., 2022).

A study affirms that HOXA10-transfected umbilical cord mesenchymal stem cells (T10-UCMSCs) outperform unmodified UCMSCs in improving endometrial healing and receptivity. Fertility tests reveal increased embryo implantation in the T10-UCMSCs group, indicating superior therapeutic outcomes for endometrial injury repair (Wu et al., 2023).

Zhu et al. describes that thin endometrial tissue hinders embryo transfer success. This study explored Cardiotrophin-1-modified bone marrow stem cell exosomes (C-BMSC-exos) for fertility improvement. C-BMSC-exo treatment enhanced tissue regeneration, neovascularization, and reduced fibrosis, boosting embryo receptivity and birth rates (Zhu et al., 2022).

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Molecular Mechanism	Study/Source	Findings/Implications
Angiogenesis	Tabeeva et al., 2023	MSCs contribute to angiogenesis in the endometrium, facilitating tissue regeneration.
Mesenchymal-Epithelial Transition	Tabeeva et al., 2023	MSCs promote mesenchymal-epithelial transition, a critical process for tissue repair.
MicroRNA Regulation	Jin-Xiang Wu et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2021; Marinero et al., 2019	Studies scrutinize microRNAs for their regulatory roles in post-transcriptional gene regulation during implantation and receptivity.
Proteomic Profiling	Sapozhak et al., 2020; Various studies	Advanced proteomic profiling unveils dynamic protein landscapes in the endometrium, shedding light on critical signaling pathways.
Extracellular Vesicles	Marinero et al., 2019; Sapozhak et al., 2020	Exploration of exosomes as carriers of molecular signals, including interferon- γ -inducible protein 10, interleukin-1 receptor antagonist, vascular endothelial growth factor, and more.
Immunomodulation	Gao et al., 2022;	MSCs demonstrate immunomodulatory effects crucial for embryo tolerance and tissue regeneration.
Growth Factor Regulation	Zhao et al., 2021; Sapozhak et al., 2020	MSCs regulate growth factors, including the EGF/Ras p21 pathway, presenting a promising therapeutic target for thin endometrium.
Inflammatory Priming	Marinero et al., 2019	Inflammatory priming of extracellular vesicles from endMSCs, indicating potential immunomodulatory effects in endometrial healing.
TGF- β Receptor Inhibition	Gurung et al., 2018	Inhibition of TGF- β receptor enhances anti-inflammatory, angiogenic, and proliferative processes in MSCs.
Paracrine Signaling	Sapozhak et al., 2020; Marinero et al., 2019; Gao et al., 2022;	Paracrine interactions between stem cells and endometrial cells contribute to improved receptivity.
Gene Expression Changes	Lu et al., 2019; Esmailzadeh et al., 2020	Changes in gene expression related to receptivity markers, impacting the establishment of pregnancy. Elevated expression of LIFR, ER, and PR in endometrium.
Epigenetic Modulation	Szukiewicz et al., 2021	Epigenetic modulation in MSCs influenced by estrogen and progesterone holds potential for preventing endometriosis.
Anti-Inflammatory Effects	Perrini et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2022	MSC-derived microvesicles exhibit anti-inflammatory effects, alleviating endometrial inflammation.
SDF-1/CXCR4 Axis	Xia et al., 2019	Electroacupuncture enhances BMSC migration through the SDF-1/CXCR4 axis, promoting endometrial repair.

Table 4: Mechanisms of MSC on Improve the Endometrial Receptivity

4.7 Delivery of MSCs for Improving Endometrial Receptivity

As described in various studies above, improving endometrial receptivity through MSC delivery is an actively researched area, with evolving protocols and diverse strategies.

Figure 10: Therapeutics Scaffold of IUI with MSCs (Cen et al., 2022)

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Pros of MSCs Delivery	Cons of MSCs Delivery
Potential for tissue repair and regeneration (Tabeeva et al., 2023, Jin-Xiang Wu et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2021; Marinaro et al., 2019)	Risk of immune rejection (Marinaro et al., 2019; Sapozhak et al., 2020, Gao et al., 2022)
Ability to modulate immune responses (Gurung et al., 2018, Gao et al., 2022)	Possibility of tumor formation (Perrini et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2022, Lu et al., 2019; Esmailzadeh et al., 2020)
Versatility in differentiation potential	Ethical concerns regarding cell sourcing
Minimal risk of tumorigenicity (Sapozhak et al., 2020; Various studies, Gao et al., 2022; Szukiewicz et al., 2021)	Uncertainty surrounding long-term effects (Tabeeva et al., 2023, Jin-Xiang Wu et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2021; Marinaro et al., 2019)
Low risk of transmitting infections (Marinaro et al., 2019; Sapozhak et al., 2020)	Variable efficacy across different conditions Lu et al., 2019; Esmailzadeh et al., 2020
Non-invasive delivery methods available (Perrini et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2022)	Limited understanding of optimal dosing and timing (Szukiewicz et al., 2021)
Potential for personalized treatments (Esmailzadeh et al., 2020)	Regulatory hurdles for clinical applications (Perrini et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2022)

Table 5: Pros and Cons of MSCs Delivery

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Delivery Method	Description
Intrauterine Infusion	Direct injection into the uterine cavity via catheter or hysteroscopic guidance. - Provides a localized delivery of MSCs to the target area.
Systemic Administration	Involves intravenous infusion or intra-arterial delivery into the uterine artery. - Allows for widespread distribution of MSCs throughout the body or targeted delivery to the uterus.
Combination Approaches	Inducing controlled endometrial injury before MSC delivery. - Co-administering cytokines/growth factors to enhance therapeutic effects. - Aims to create a more conducive environment for MSC action.
Use of Biocompatible Scaffolds	Incorporates three-dimensional structures for MSC delivery. - Aids in cell retention and optimization of the local microenvironment. - Offers a supportive framework for MSCs to exert their regenerative effects.
Monitoring and Imaging Techniques	Utilizes ultrasound or magnetic resonance imaging for tracking MSC location and distribution. - Essential for proper targeting and ensuring the effectiveness of the delivered MSCs.
Preclinical Studies and Trials	Thorough evaluation of safety and efficacy through preclinical studies and clinical trials. - Considers individual patient factors and specific causes of infertility to tailor the delivery method.
Consultation with Professionals	Paramount for personalized advice and treatment planning. - Involves consultation with medical professionals or reproductive specialists to guide patients in navigating the dynamic and evolving field of MSC therapy.

Table 6: Delivery Methods of MSCs in Various Modalities

4.8 Evaluating Mesenchymal Stem Cell Therapy for Endometrial Receptivity

Evaluating MSC therapy for uterine endothelial injury involves a comprehensive approach, integrating diverse monitoring and evaluation parameters. This aims to confirm improvements through both traditional and molecular studies (Bajpai et al., 2023).

Imaging studies, such as regular ultrasound examinations, provide valuable insights into changes in uterine morphology, blood flow, and the thickness of the endometrial lining (Bajpai et al., 2023).

Doppler ultrasound is employed to assess blood flow in uterine arteries, helping determine improvements in vascular function. (Christodoulou et al., 2018)

Biopsy and histological analysis, including endometrial biopsies, provide insights into tissue structure, vascularization, and cellular composition changes. Immunohistochemistry assesses endothelial cell marker expression like CD31 or vWF, aiding in blood vessel regeneration assessment (Cen et al., 2022).

Biomarkers, such as circulating markers associated with endothelial function and regeneration (e.g., VEGF, angiopoietin-1), are measured to understand the molecular changes in the uterine cavity. Additionally, the assessment of inflammatory markers aids in evaluating the overall inflammatory response.

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Functional tests, like the ERA or molecular marker analysis, gauge MSC therapy's success in preparing the uterine environment for implantation. Patient outcomes, including pregnancy rates and menstrual cycle regularity, provide clinical indicators.

Tracking successful pregnancies and live births is crucial, alongside improvements in cycle regularity and associated symptoms. Assessing symptom relief, especially for endothelial injury-related issues like pain or abnormal bleeding, and standardized quality of life assessments contribute to evaluating patients' well-being during MSC therapy.

Follow-up assessments, including long-term evaluations and periodic follow-ups, ensure sustained improvements and allow for adjustments to treatment plans if necessary.

A comprehensive study or clinical trial, incorporating appropriate controls and a sufficiently large sample size, is crucial for drawing meaningful conclusions.

Incorporating molecular studies is essential in advancing our understanding of the effects of MSC therapy (Corradetti et al., 2014).

Gene expression analysis, such as RNA sequencing, provides a comprehensive view of changes in the transcriptome post-MSC therapy. Protein expression studies,

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employing techniques like western blotting, assess alterations in specific proteins associated with endothelial function (Darz et al., 2016).

Immunohistochemistry and immunofluorescence contribute to the identification and quantification of specific proteins within tissue samples, aiding in understanding cellular and tissue changes (Wang et al., 2021).

Cytokine and growth factor analysis, through methods like enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), offer insights into the inflammatory and regenerative response in the uterine microenvironment (Tamadon et al., 2017).

Molecular studies also encompass DNA methylation studies, utilizing DNA methylation arrays to analyze changes in methylation patterns influencing gene expression and cellular function.

MicroRNA profiling, through arrays or sequencing, examines alterations in microRNA expression, which plays a role in regulating gene expression and cellular processes (Cen et al., 2022).

Next-generation sequencing (NGS) techniques, including whole genome sequencing (WGS) and whole exome sequencing (WES), provide a comprehensive analysis of genetic variations and mutations that may influence treatment outcomes.

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Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-Seq) allows for a detailed examination of individual cells within a heterogeneous population, providing insights into cellular diversity and responses (Zhang et al., 2016).

The selection of specific molecular studies depends on research objectives, available technologies, and advancements in the field. Researchers often combine multiple techniques to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the molecular changes occurring after MSC therapy (Tabeeva et al., 2023).

Staying informed about the latest literature and consulting with experts in the field ensures the utilization of the most current methodologies (Zhao et al., 2021).

5 Ethics on Using MSCs

Over the last two decades, stem cell therapy, particularly using MSCs, has become a promising frontier in regenerative medicine, drawing significant attention due to their unique advantages among human tissue-derived stem cells (Zakrzewski W et al., 2019).

MSCs provide accessible, easily isolated, and scalable cells. They differentiate into diverse cell types, secrete regenerative substances, and actively contribute to tissue repair. Their immunoregulatory properties enable ethical autografts and allografts, with reduced immunogenicity. However, they have a finite replicative lifespan (Zhankina et al., 2021).

Clinical MSC therapy encounters challenge due to population heterogeneity. Variability in culture conditions, donors, passage, and cell density impedes generalization across studies. Safety concerns encompass tumorigenicity, with potential for malignant transformation during in vitro culturing or in vivo immunosuppressive environments (Barkholt et al., 2013).

Although no documented cases of tumor development in individuals undergoing MSC treatment exist, continuous research and long-term patient monitoring are crucial to assess potential tumorigenic risks associated with MSC therapy.

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MSC therapy poses a risk of embolization, leading to clot formation and hindering homing. Some studies report pulmonary embolism post intravenous MSC infusions. To address this, protocols with anticoagulant therapy like low-dose heparin are explored (Jung et al., 2013).

In conclusion, addressing MSC therapy challenges like heterogeneity, tumorigenicity, and embolization is crucial for clinical success (Corradetti et al., 2014). Ongoing research and vigilant patient monitoring are essential for unlocking MSC-based regenerative medicine's full potential (Mirfakhraie et al., 2023).

Selecting the optimal method for MSC collection requires considering several factors. Patient suitability, based on medical condition and history, influences the choice of tissue source (Christodoulou et al., 2018).

Ethical and regulatory compliance is essential. Practical aspects like tissue availability and safety must be evaluated. Collection should be performed by experienced professionals (Barkholt et al., 2013).

Overall, deciding on MSC collection involves consulting healthcare providers and staying updated on advancements in MSC-based therapies.

6 Result

This literature review thoroughly explains the complex molecular mechanisms involving MSCs and their crucial role in enhancing endometrial receptivity (Tamadon et al., 2017).

Using advanced techniques like microRNA analysis, proteomic profiling, and transcriptomics, the review identifies consistent diagnostic biomarkers in receptive endometria (Barkholt et al., 2013).

MSCs, derived from diverse sources including menstrual blood-derived stromal cells (menSCs), bone marrow, and umbilical cord, exhibit therapeutic potential by modulating key signaling pathways and fostering endometrial regeneration. Adherence to the International Association of Cell Therapy criteria ensures the reliability of MSCs (Bajpai et al., 2023).

In-depth investigations, spanning from animal models to clinical cases, consistently demonstrate post-MSc transplantation improvements in endometrial thickness and receptivity.

Paracrine interactions between MSC-derived microvesicles and endometrial cells exhibit anti-inflammatory effects, laying the groundwork for mitigating endometrial inflammation (Darz et al., 2016).

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Aspect	Summary
Molecular Mechanisms	Elucidates intricate molecular mechanisms surrounding MSCs and their role in augmenting endometrial receptivity through microRNA analysis, proteomic profiling, and transcriptomics.
MSC Sources	MSCs derived from various sources like menSCs, bone marrow, and umbilical cord exhibit therapeutic potential in endometrial regeneration.
Therapy Efficacy	Post-MSCTransplantation improvements in endometrial thickness and receptivity observed consistently in animal models and clinical cases.
Paracrine Interactions	MSC-derived microvesicles exhibit anti-inflammatory effects, contributing to mitigating endometrial inflammation.
Synergistic Approaches	Combining MSC transplantation with techniques like electroacupuncture or thermoresponsive biomaterials enhances therapeutic outcomes.
Delivery Methods	Various MSC delivery methods explored emphasizing a multifaceted approach in evaluating therapy efficacy.
Evaluation Parameters	Parameters include imaging studies, biopsy and histological analysis, biomarkers, functional tests, and patient outcomes.
Molecular Studies	Molecular studies like RNA sequencing, western blotting, immunohistochemistry, DNA methylation studies, and next-generation sequencing scrutinized to understand genetic variations post-MSCTherapy.
Ethical Considerations	Highlighted advantages and challenges of MSC usage such as heterogeneity, tumorigenicity, and embolization risks, emphasizing the necessity for ongoing research and extended patient monitoring.
MSC Collection Methods	Complexity discussed in determining suitable methods considering patient suitability, ethical and regulatory considerations, safety, and efficacy, underscoring the pivotal role of clinical expertise in execution.
Conclusion	Provides a cohesive exploration of MSC therapy for improving endometrial receptivity, emphasizing diverse strategies, ongoing research, and international standards for addressing infertility associated with endothelial injury.

Table7: Over all Major Detail of Literature

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Additionally, synergistic approaches such as combining MSC transplantation with electroacupuncture or thermoresponsive biomaterials enhance therapeutic outcomes (Wang et al., 2021).

This collective evidence underscores the clinical promise of MSC-based interventions, presenting targeted and personalized approaches to address endometrial receptivity challenges in reproductive medicine (Darz et al., 2016).

The literature review further explores MSC therapy as a prospective solution for enhancing endometrial receptivity and resolving infertility issues associated with uterine endothelial injury (Corradetti et al., 2014).

Various MSC delivery methods are examined, emphasizing the importance of a multifaceted approach in evaluating therapy efficacy. Evaluation parameters discussed encompass imaging studies, biopsy and histological analysis, biomarkers, functional tests, and patient outcomes (Zhuang et al., 2022).

Molecular studies, including RNA sequencing, western blotting, immunohistochemistry, DNA methylation studies, and next-generation sequencing, are scrutinized to advance our comprehension of genetic variations and alterations post-MSC therapy (Chen et al., 2022).

Ethical considerations related to MSC usage, including advantages and challenges such as heterogeneity, tumorigenicity, and embolization risks, are thoughtfully

highlighted. The review underscores the necessity for ongoing research and extended patient monitoring to address these concerns and fully unlock the potential of MSC-based regenerative medicine.

Moreover, the complexity of determining the most suitable method for MSC collection is discussed, considering patient suitability, ethical and regulatory considerations, safety, and efficacy. The review emphasizes the pivotal role of clinical expertise in ensuring the proper execution of MSC collection procedures.

In conclusion, this literature review provides a comprehensive and cohesive exploration of MSC therapy for improving endometrial receptivity, encompassing delivery methods, evaluation parameters, molecular studies, ethical considerations, and MSC collection methods.

The integration of diverse strategies, coupled with ongoing research efforts, is imperative for advancing the field and realizing the potential of MSC-based regenerative medicine in addressing infertility associated with endothelial injury on an international standard.

7 Discussion

Endometrial receptivity, crucial for fertility, highlights the uterine lining's ability to support embryo implantation (Bajpai et al., 2023). This temporal event, in the implantation window during the latter part of the menstrual cycle, requires precise hormonal fluctuations and structural modifications within the endometrium (Rungsiwiwut et al., 2021). Endometrial receptivity is vital in assisted reproductive technologies, where issues like thin endometrium or inflammation can hinder implantation. MSCs, with regenerative and immunomodulatory properties, show promise in enhancing receptivity (Barkholt et al., 2013). Derived from sources like bone marrow and adipose tissue, MSCs can modulate inflammation, stimulate angiogenesis, and optimize the endometrial microenvironment.

Advanced molecular investigations, including miRNA profiling and proteomic analyses, offer diagnostic insights into receptivity's dynamics. Ongoing research emphasizes MSCs' therapeutic potential, particularly menstrual blood-derived MSCs, for conditions like thin endometrium. Ethical considerations align with established criteria, though challenges related to heterogeneity and tumorigenicity warrant ongoing scrutiny. Optimal MSC collection methods consider patient suitability, ethical standards, tissue source availability, and safety assessments. Clinical expertise is essential for guiding decisions in regenerative medicine.

8 Clinical Implication

The elucidation of endometrial receptivity and the burgeoning role of MSCs bear notable clinical implications in the domain of reproductive medicine.

A nuanced understanding of endometrial receptivity, facilitated by molecular investigations and advanced diagnostic tools, holds promise for refining the assessment of implantation windows and optimizing the success rates of assisted reproductive technologies (Zhang et al., 2016).

Aspect	Summary
Clinical Implications	Understanding endometrial receptivity through molecular investigations and advanced diagnostic tools can refine implantation window assessment and improve success rates of assisted reproductive technologies (Zhang et al., 2016).
Therapeutic Potential of MSCs	MSCs offer a novel approach for addressing challenges related to thin endometrium and recurrent implantation failure. Their regenerative and immunomodulatory properties, demonstrated in preclinical and clinical studies, can enhance endometrial receptivity and alleviate infertility factors (Zhang et al., 2016).
Ethical Considerations	Ethical considerations surrounding MSC usage require a judicious approach, ensuring compliance with established criteria and continuous safety scrutiny (Rungsiwiwut et al., 2021).
Integration into Clinical Practice	Integration of MSC-based interventions into clinical practice can offer tailored therapeutic strategies for individuals facing complex reproductive challenges, contributing to advancements in fertility treatments (Rungsiwiwut et al., 2021).

Table 8: Brief of Clinical Implications

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The therapeutic potential of MSCs, particularly in addressing challenges associated with a thin endometrium, offers a novel avenue for improving outcomes in patients experiencing recurrent implantation failure (Abuwala & Tal, 2021).

The regenerative and immunomodulatory properties of MSCs, as demonstrated in preclinical and clinical studies, underscore their potential application in enhancing endometrial receptivity and mitigating factors contributing to infertility (Bajpai et al., 2023).

Additionally, the ethical considerations surrounding the use of MSCs necessitate a judicious approach, ensuring compliance with established criteria and continuous scrutiny of safety profiles (Costela-Ruiz et al., 2022).

As research advances, the integration of MSC-based interventions into clinical practice may offer a tailored and effective therapeutic strategy for individuals facing complex reproductive challenges, ultimately contributing to advancements in fertility treatments (Rungsiwiwut et al., 2021).

9 Future Research

Future research on endometrial receptivity and MSCs aims to explore molecular mechanisms using advanced omics and single-cell analyses (Cen et al., 2022). Studies will optimize MSC therapeutic potential for challenges like recurrent implantation failure and thin endometrium, refining isolation, characterization, and transplantation protocols (Corradetti et al., 2014).

Prospective studies may develop targeted diagnostic tools based on molecular biomarkers for precise embryo implantation timing, enhancing assisted reproductive technology success (Corradetti et al., 2014).

The global MSCs market is rapidly expanding within regenerative medicine, driven by increased research, prevalence of chronic diseases, and demand for cell-based therapies and Figure 11 illustrates MSCs market value (Grand View Research, 2022).

Figure 11: MSCs Market Statistics (Grand View Research, 2022)

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Applications include orthopedics, cardiovascular diseases, autoimmune disorders, and wound healing. Collaborations and initiatives shape the market, with regulatory frameworks and ethics influencing its landscape.

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Molecular Mechanisms	Elucidates intricate molecular mechanisms surrounding MSCs and their role in augmenting endometrial receptivity through microRNA analysis, proteomic profiling, and transcriptomics.
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Therapy Efficacy	Post-MSC transplantation improvements in endometrial thickness and receptivity observed consistently in animal models and clinical cases.
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Synergistic Approaches	Combining MSC transplantation with techniques like electroacupuncture or thermoresponsive biomaterials enhances therapeutic outcomes.
Delivery Methods	Various MSC delivery methods explored emphasizing a multifaceted approach in evaluating therapy efficacy.
Evaluation Parameters	Parameters include imaging studies, biopsy and histological analysis, biomarkers, functional tests, and patient outcomes.
Molecular Studies	Molecular studies like RNA sequencing, western blotting, immunohistochemistry, DNA methylation studies, and next-generation sequencing scrutinized to understand genetic variations post-MS therapy.
Ethical Considerations	Highlighted advantages and challenges of MSC usage such as heterogeneity, tumorigenicity, and embolization risks, emphasizing the necessity for ongoing research and extended patient monitoring.
MSC Collection Methods	Complexity discussed in determining suitable methods considering patient suitability, ethical and regulatory considerations, safety, and efficacy, underscoring the pivotal role of clinical expertise in execution.
Conclusion	Provides a cohesive exploration of MSC therapy for improving endometrial receptivity, emphasizing diverse strategies, ongoing research, and international standards for addressing infertility associated with endothelial injury.

Table 9: Future Research Aspects

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MSC therapies address unmet medical needs, emphasizing innovation and clinical translation. Ethical considerations, safety profiles, including tumorigenic risks, MSC characterization standardization, and long-term patient monitoring, are crucial themes for future research.

Overall, interdisciplinary research combining molecular biology, stem cell biology, and clinical medicine promises to revolutionize fertility treatments.

10 Conclusion

In conclusion, research on endometrial receptivity and MSCs in reproductive medicine offers a multifaceted path for future exploration. Advancements in understanding receptivity, driven by molecular studies and diagnostic progress, enable more nuanced assessments of implantation timing. MSCs' therapeutic potential, especially in tackling challenges like recurrent implantation failure and thin endometrium, promises to reshape clinical approaches in reproductive health.

Menstrual Cycle Phase	Days	Endometrial Receptivity	Mesenchymal Stem Cells Application
Menstrual (Days 1-5)	1-5	Low estrogen and progesterone, shedding of the endometrial lining	-
Proliferative (Days 6-14)	6-14	Rising estrogen levels, thickening of the endometrial lining, increased blood flow	Potential infusion of mesenchymal stem cells to support tissue regeneration and vascularization
Ovulatory (Day 15)	15	Surge in luteinizing hormone (LH), ovulation occurs	Mesenchymal stem cells may play a role in modulating the immune response and promoting tissue repair post-ovulation
Early Luteal (Days 16-18)	16-18	Increased progesterone, glandular and stromal changes, vascularization	Possible application of mesenchymal stem cells to enhance progesterone effects and support tissue remodeling
Mid-Luteal (Days 19-23)	19-23	Sustained high progesterone, increased glandular secretion, spiral artery development	Mesenchymal stem cells may contribute to the maintenance of a supportive microenvironment for potential embryo implantation
Late Luteal (Days 24-28)	24-28	Declining progesterone if no pregnancy, pre-menstrual changes, breakdown of the endometrial tissue	Mesenchymal stem cells might be applied to promote tissue repair and regeneration, potentially preparing the endometrium for the next cycle

Table 10: MSCs and Different Phase of Menstrual Cycle

Fertility Breakthrough: Mesenchymal Stem Cells and Enhanced Endometrial

Receptivity - A Comprehensive Review

Future research will explore molecular mechanisms governing endometrial receptivity using advanced technologies. Refining MSC-based interventions and diagnostic tools for personalized embryo implantation timing in assisted reproductive technologies are key.

Ethical considerations and safety profiles in MSC use will remain focal points, alongside addressing potential risks and standardizing criteria. The interdisciplinary convergence of molecular and stem cell biology with clinical reproductive medicine promises tailored therapeutic solutions for fertility challenges.

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<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3724/abbs.2021015>

12 Acknowledgement

This study has used the major illustrations after the formal consent obtained from the respective authors via email and we really appreciate them for their generous support and cited them accordingly in this literature review.

Dr Lusine Aghajanova, Clinical Associate Professor, Director, Third Party Reproduction Program Director, Endometrial Health Program, Associate Program Director, REI Fellowship, Division of Reproductive Endocrinology and Infertility, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Stanford University School of Medicine

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Fertility Breakthrough: Mesenchymal Stem Cells and Enhanced Endometrial

Receptivity - A Comprehensive Review

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The Chinese University of Hong Kong Academic Honesty Declaration Statement

Submission Details

Student Name	KANAGARATNAM Pakeerathan (s1155179738)		
Year and Term	2023-2024 Term 2		
Course	RMCE-6003--J01 Literature review		
Assignment Marker	Professor CHUNG Pui Wah Jacqueline		
Submitted File Name	Final thesis for submission.docx		
Submission Type	Individual		
Assignment Number	1	Due Date (provided by student)	2024-04-18
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